

CERTIFICATE

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

DARAYEVA SEVARA

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

**THE IMPACT OF ALISHER NAVOI AND ZAHIRIDDIN MUHAMMAD
BOBUR'S MASTERPIECES ON RENAISSANCE IN XV CENTURY AS
WELL AS THEIR ROLE IN SOCIETY.**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir: A.A. Abdurahmonov

Яндекс

@mail

Google

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